

Residual Divisor Certificates for the Erdős–Straus Equation

A Six-Class Sieve Modulo 840 and a Jacobi-Symbol Barrier

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Abstract

For a prime p and an integer $a > p/4$, write $R = 4a - p$ and $N = pa$. The Erdős–Straus completion problem

$$\frac{4}{p} = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$$

with this fixed first denominator is equivalent to the existence of a divisor $d \mid N^2$ satisfying a single congruence $d \equiv -N \pmod{R}$. This note records the resulting residual-shell calculus. In the hard prime class $p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}$, every shell has $R \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ and the divisor search reduces to three residue targets attached to the possible p -adic origins $1, p, p^2$ of the divisor. We prove an unconditional modulo-840 sieve: if $p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}$ is not a simultaneous quadratic residue modulo 5 and modulo 7, then the equation is solved already at residual $R = 3$ or $R = 7$. Hence any hard-class prime requiring $R \geq 11$ lies in the six unit square classes

$$p \equiv 1, 121, 169, 289, 361, 529 \pmod{840}.$$

We also formulate a Jacobi-symbol obstruction which gives a sufficient algebraic reason for an entire residual shell to fail. These results are reductions and obstruction criteria; they do not prove the full Erdős–Straus conjecture.

Keywords. Erdős–Straus conjecture; Egyptian fractions; divisor certificates; quadratic residues; congruence identities; Jacobi symbols.

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1 Background and notation

The Erdős–Straus conjecture asserts that for every integer $n \geq 2$ there are positive integers x, y, z such that

$$\frac{4}{n} = \frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{y} + \frac{1}{z}. \tag{1}$$

The conjecture appears in Erdős’s work on unit-fraction equations [3]. Classical congruence identities, especially those organized by Mordell [5], solve many residue classes. Quantitative work of Elsholtz and Tao studies the average number of solutions for prime denominators [2]. A modern computational verification to 10^{17} using modular equations is described by Salez [6]. The affine surfaces associated with (1) have also been studied from the point of view of integral points and the Brauer–Manin obstruction [1].

The purpose of this note is narrower. We isolate a residual divisor-certificate calculus and use it to prove an exact six-class reduction modulo 840 for the residual search beyond $R = 7$.

Throughout, p denotes an odd prime unless otherwise stated. For a chosen first denominator a , put

$$R := 4a - p, \quad N := pa. \quad (2)$$

The integer R will be called the *residual*. In the hard prime class $p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}$, integrality of $a = (p + R)/4$ forces $R \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

2 The residual divisor certificate

Lemma 2.1 (Fixed- a divisor criterion). *Let p be prime and let a be a positive integer with $R = 4a - p > 0$ and $N = pa$. Suppose $\gcd(R, N) = 1$. Then*

$$\frac{4}{p} = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$$

for positive integers b, c if and only if there is a divisor $d \mid N^2$ such that

$$d \equiv -N \pmod{R}. \quad (3)$$

Given such a d , let $e = N^2/d$ and set

$$b = \frac{N + d}{R}, \quad c = \frac{N + e}{R}. \quad (4)$$

Then b, c are positive integers and give the required identity.

Proof. The fixed- a remainder is

$$\frac{4}{p} - \frac{1}{a} = \frac{4a - p}{pa} = \frac{R}{N}.$$

Thus the problem is equivalent to $R/N = 1/b + 1/c$. Multiplying by Nbc gives

$$Rbc = N(b + c).$$

Equivalently,

$$(Rb - N)(Rc - N) = N^2.$$

Hence $d := Rb - N$ is a positive divisor of N^2 satisfying $d \equiv -N \pmod{R}$, and $e := Rc - N = N^2/d$.

Conversely, if $d \mid N^2$ and $d \equiv -N \pmod{R}$, put $e = N^2/d$. Because $\gcd(N, R) = 1$,

$$e \equiv \frac{N^2}{-N} \equiv -N \pmod{R}.$$

So (4) is integral. Substituting $d = Rb - N$ and $e = Rc - N$ into $de = N^2$ gives $Rbc = N(b + c)$, hence $R/N = 1/b + 1/c$. \square

For residual shells $R \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, one usually fixes

$$a_R := \frac{p + R}{4}. \quad (5)$$

Then $p = 4a_R - R$, so

$$p \equiv 4a_R \pmod{R}. \quad (6)$$

Every divisor of $N^2 = p^2 a_R^2$ has the form $p^i u$ with $i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ and $u \mid a_R^2$. This gives the following exact finite residue test.

Theorem 2.2 (Three-origin residual criterion). *Let $R \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, $a = (p + R)/4$, and assume $\gcd(R, pa) = 1$. Shell R gives an Erdős–Straus certificate if and only if there exists a divisor $u \mid a^2$ such that at least one of the following three congruences holds:*

$$\begin{aligned} u &\equiv -4a^2 \pmod{R}, && \text{(1-origin)} \\ u &\equiv -a \pmod{R}, && \text{(}p\text{-origin)} \\ u &\equiv -4^{-1} \pmod{R}. && \text{(}p^2\text{-origin)} \end{aligned}$$

The corresponding certificate divisors are respectively

$$d = u, \quad d = pu, \quad d = p^2u.$$

Proof. By Lemma 2.1, we need $p^i u \equiv -pa \pmod{R}$. Using $p \equiv 4a \pmod{R}$ gives three cases. If $i = 0$, then $u \equiv -pa \equiv -4a^2$. If $i = 1$, cancellation of p gives $u \equiv -a$. If $i = 2$, then

$$p^2 u \equiv -pa \iff (4a)^2 u \equiv -(4a)a \iff u \equiv -4^{-1} \pmod{R},$$

using $\gcd(a, R) = 1$. This proves the equivalence. \square

Remark 2.3. *Theorem 2.2 turns the shell- R problem into a divisor-residue membership problem inside $(\mathbb{Z}/R\mathbb{Z})^\times$. Define*

$$D_R(a) := \{u \bmod R : u \mid a^2\} \subseteq (\mathbb{Z}/R\mathbb{Z})^\times.$$

Then shell R works exactly when

$$D_R(a) \cap \{-4a^2, -a, -4^{-1}\} \neq \emptyset. \tag{7}$$

This is the exact obstruction. Quadratic-character obstructions are coarser quotients of (7).

3 Standard prime reductions and the hard class

Lemma 3.1 (Composite reduction). *If (1) has a solution for p and $p \mid n$, then it has a solution for n .*

Proof. Write $n = mp$. If $4/p = 1/x + 1/y + 1/z$, then

$$\frac{4}{n} = \frac{1}{mx} + \frac{1}{my} + \frac{1}{mz}.$$

\square

Thus the conjecture reduces to prime denominators. The following elementary reductions isolate the usual hard prime class.

Proposition 3.2 (Reduction to $p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}$). *Let p be prime. The Erdős–Straus equation is solved explicitly for $p = 2$ and for every odd prime $p \not\equiv 1 \pmod{24}$. Hence the remaining prime class is*

$$p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}.$$

Proof. The case $p = 2$ is immediate:

$$\frac{4}{2} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}.$$

If $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, take $a = (p + 1)/4$. Then $R = 1$ and

$$\frac{4}{p} = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{1}{2pa} + \frac{1}{2pa}.$$

If $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, then

$$\frac{4}{p} = \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{(p+1)/3} + \frac{1}{p(p+1)/3}.$$

It remains to cover primes $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ and $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ which are not $1 \pmod{24}$. Such primes have $p \equiv 13 \pmod{24}$, hence $p \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$. Put $R = 3$ and $a = (p + 3)/4$. Since $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, one has $a \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ and $N = pa \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Since $p \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$, the integer a is even, so $d = 2 \mid a^2 \mid N^2$ and

$$d = 2 \equiv -N \pmod{3}.$$

Lemma 2.1 gives a certificate. □

The first residual shell in the hard class has an exact factorization criterion.

Theorem 3.3 (Exact $R = 3$ criterion). *Let $p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}$ and set*

$$a = \frac{p + 3}{4}.$$

Then shell $R = 3$ works if and only if a has a prime divisor $q \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$. Equivalently, shell $R = 3$ fails if and only if every prime divisor of a is congruent to $1 \pmod{3}$.

Proof. For $p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}$, one has $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ and $a \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Hence $N = pa \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ and the divisor target is

$$d \equiv -N \equiv 2 \pmod{3}.$$

Because $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, powers of p do not affect the residue class. Therefore a divisor $d \mid p^2 a^2$ has residue $2 \pmod{3}$ exactly when the a^2 -part contains a prime factor congruent to $2 \pmod{3}$. Since $a \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, all prime factors of a are congruent to 1 or $2 \pmod{3}$, and the result follows. □

Corollary 3.4. *If $p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}$ and $p \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$, then shell $R = 3$ works.*

Proof. For $a = (p + 3)/4$, the congruence $p \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$ gives $a \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. Since $5 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, Theorem 3.3 applies. Equivalently, the explicit certificate divisor is $d = 5$. □

4 A six-class sieve modulo 840

The hard residue classes modulo $840 = 24 \cdot 5 \cdot 7$ are the classes

$$p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}, \quad p \in (\mathbb{Z}/5\mathbb{Z})^\times, \quad p \in (\mathbb{Z}/7\mathbb{Z})^\times.$$

There are $4 \cdot 6 = 24$ such classes. The quadratic residues modulo 5 are 1, 4; those modulo 7 are 1, 2, 4. Therefore the simultaneous square sector has size $2 \cdot 3 = 6$.

Lemma 4.1 (The six square classes). *Among residue classes $p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}$ which are prime to 840, the classes which are quadratic residues modulo both 5 and 7 are precisely*

$$1, 121, 169, 289, 361, 529 \pmod{840}. \quad (8)$$

Proof. The classes are obtained by the Chinese remainder theorem from

$$p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}, \quad p \equiv 1, 4 \pmod{5}, \quad p \equiv 1, 2, 4 \pmod{7}.$$

Solving these six CRT systems gives exactly (8). □

Theorem 4.2 (Non-square modulo 840 theorem). *Let p be prime with*

$$p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}.$$

If p is not one of the six classes (8), then the Erdős–Straus equation has a certificate with residual $R = 3$ or residual $R = 7$.

Proof. By Lemma 4.1, if p is outside the six classes, then either p is a quadratic non-residue modulo 5 or p is a quadratic non-residue modulo 7.

If $p \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$, Corollary 3.4 gives a certificate at $R = 3$.

Next assume p is a quadratic non-residue modulo 7. Put

$$R = 7, \quad a = \frac{p+7}{4}.$$

Let $r \equiv p \pmod{7}$. Since $4^{-1} \equiv 2 \pmod{7}$,

$$a \equiv 2r \pmod{7}, \quad N = pa \equiv 2r^2 \pmod{7}.$$

The divisor target is

$$d \equiv -N \equiv -2r^2 \pmod{7}.$$

The non-residues modulo 7 are $r \in \{3, 5, 6\}$. They are covered as follows:

r	$-2r^2 \pmod{7}$	certificate divisor d
3	3	p
5	6	$2a$
6	5	a

For $r = 3$, $d = p$ has the target residue. For $r = 5$, one has $a \equiv 3 \pmod{7}$ and $2a \equiv 6 \pmod{7}$; also $p \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$, so $a = (p+7)/4$ is even and $2a \mid a^2$. For $r = 6$, one has $a \equiv 5 \pmod{7}$, so $d = a$ works. Thus $R = 7$ works whenever p is a non-residue modulo 7.

It remains to handle the case $p \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$ and p is a square modulo 7. Again use $R = 7$ and $a = (p+7)/4$. Since $p \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$,

$$a \equiv \frac{p+7}{4} \equiv \frac{3+2}{4} \equiv 0 \pmod{5}.$$

Also $p \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$, so a is even. Since p is square modulo 7,

$$r \in \{1, 2, 4\}.$$

The three cases are:

r	$a \pmod{7}$	$-2r^2 \pmod{7}$	certificate divisor d
1	2	5	5
2	4	6	$5a$
4	1	3	$10a$

The listed divisors all divide a^2 : $5 \mid a$, $5a \mid a^2$, and $10a \mid a^2$ because $2 \mid a$ and $5 \mid a$. Each has the target residue modulo 7. Lemma 2.1 completes the proof. \square

Corollary 4.3 (Residual-tail confinement). *Let $p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}$ be prime. If the first successful residual shell satisfies $R \geq 11$, then*

$$p \equiv 1, 121, 169, 289, 361, 529 \pmod{840}.$$

Equivalently, any search beyond $R = 7$ is analytically confined to the six simultaneous square classes modulo 840.

Proof. This is the contrapositive of Theorem 4.2. \square

5 The finite character object behind the $24 \rightarrow 6$ collapse

Let

$$V_{840} := \{r \pmod{840} : r \equiv 1 \pmod{24}, \gcd(r, 840) = 1\}.$$

By the Chinese remainder theorem,

$$V_{840} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/5\mathbb{Z})^\times \times (\mathbb{Z}/7\mathbb{Z})^\times \cong C_4 \times C_6. \quad (9)$$

Hence $|V_{840}| = 24$. Let

$$V_{840}^{\text{sq}} := \{r \in V_{840} : r \in \text{QR}(5), r \in \text{QR}(7)\}.$$

Then

$$V_{840}^{\text{sq}} \cong C_2 \times C_3, \quad |V_{840}^{\text{sq}}| = 6.$$

The quotient

$$V_{840}/V_{840}^{\text{sq}} \cong C_2 \times C_2 \quad (10)$$

is detected by the two quadratic characters

$$\chi_5(r) = \left(\frac{r}{5}\right), \quad \chi_7(r) = \left(\frac{r}{7}\right).$$

Theorem 4.2 says that residual shells $R = 3$ and $R = 7$ delete all three non-principal character sectors of this quotient, leaving only the square subgroup V_{840}^{sq} . This is the precise finite character-theoretic content of the observed $24 \rightarrow 6$ reduction.

One may package the shell search as a family of labeled divisor-residue graphs. For fixed R and $a = (p + R)/4$, put vertices

$$D_R(a) = \{u \pmod{R} : u \mid a^2\} \subseteq (\mathbb{Z}/R\mathbb{Z})^\times$$

and mark the three targets

$$T_R(a) := \{-4a^2, -a, -4^{-1}\} \subseteq (\mathbb{Z}/R\mathbb{Z})^\times.$$

Then shell R works precisely when $D_R(a)$ hits $T_R(a)$. The six-class theorem identifies a first-level character quotient where the early shells force a hit unless p lies in V_{840}^{sq} .

6 A Jacobi-symbol barrier

The exact obstruction is the divisor-set miss (7). A useful sufficient obstruction is obtained by passing to the Jacobi character.

Theorem 6.1 (Jacobi-symbol barrier). *Let p be prime, $R \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, $a = (p + R)/4$, and $\gcd(R, pa) = 1$. Suppose every prime divisor $q \mid a$ satisfies*

$$\left(\frac{q}{R}\right) = 1. \quad (11)$$

Then residual shell R cannot give an Erdős–Straus certificate.

Proof. Let $\chi_R(x) = \left(\frac{x}{R}\right)$ be the Jacobi symbol. Since $R \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$,

$$\chi_R(-1) = -1.$$

By hypothesis, every divisor $u \mid a^2$ satisfies $\chi_R(u) = 1$, and also $\chi_R(a) = 1$. Since $p \equiv 4a \pmod{R}$ and 4 is a square,

$$\chi_R(p) = \chi_R(4a) = \chi_R(a) = 1.$$

Therefore every divisor $d \mid p^2a^2$ has $\chi_R(d) = 1$. But a certificate divisor must satisfy $d \equiv -N = -pa \pmod{R}$, whose Jacobi symbol is

$$\chi_R(-pa) = \chi_R(-1)\chi_R(p)\chi_R(a) = -1.$$

This is impossible. □

Remark 6.2. *The barrier is only sufficient. If some prime factor of a has Jacobi symbol -1 modulo R , then the character obstruction opens, but the exact divisor-residue set $D_R(a)$ may still miss all three targets. Thus the hierarchy is*

$$\text{Jacobi obstruction} \subsetneq \text{exact divisor-residue obstruction.}$$

7 Universal identity and an illustrative certificate

The divisor certificate gives a uniform identity schema. Let $R \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, $a = (p + R)/4$, and suppose $u \mid a^2$, $i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ satisfy

$$p^i u \equiv -pa \pmod{R}.$$

Then

$$\frac{4}{p} = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{1}{(pa + p^i u)/R} + \frac{1}{(pa + p^{2-i} a^2/u)/R}. \quad (12)$$

This is just Lemma 2.1 with $d = p^i u$.

Example 7.1 (A p -origin certificate). *For*

$$p = 8803369, \quad R = 107,$$

one has

$$a = \frac{p + R}{4} = 2200869 = 3^2 \cdot 11^2 \cdot 43 \cdot 47.$$

The divisor

$$d = p \cdot 11^2$$

has p -origin. Equivalently, in Theorem 2.2 one takes $i = 1$ and $u = 11^2$. Since

$$11^2 \equiv -a \pmod{107},$$

this gives the certificate

$$\frac{4}{8803369} = \frac{1}{2200869} + \frac{1}{181085300330} + \frac{1}{3293760527702370}.$$

8 Consequences and exact remaining problem

The results above imply the following unconditional reduction.

Corollary 8.1 (Six-class prime reduction). *The Erdős–Straus conjecture is equivalent to its restriction to primes*

$$p \equiv 1, 121, 169, 289, 361, 529 \pmod{840}.$$

More precisely, all other integers are solved either by composite descent, by the elementary reductions of Proposition 3.2, or by the residual certificates $R = 3, 7$ from Theorem 4.2.

Proof. By Lemma 3.1, it suffices to solve prime denominators. Proposition 3.2 solves all primes outside $p \equiv 1 \pmod{24}$. Theorem 4.2 solves the hard-class primes outside the six square classes modulo 840. \square

Thus the remaining problem can be stated in a shell-by-shell finite form. For primes p in the six classes, define

$$a_R(p) = \frac{p + R}{4}, \quad R = 3, 7, 11, 15, \dots$$

The first successful residual is the first $R \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ for which

$$D_R(a_R(p)) \cap \{-4a_R(p)^2, -a_R(p), -4^{-1}\} \neq \emptyset.$$

A proof of the full conjecture by this method would require proving that such an R always occurs. The Jacobi barrier explains a mechanism for forced shell failure; the exact divisor-residue obstruction is the object which must ultimately be controlled.

References

- [1] M. Bright and D. Loughran, *Brauer–Manin obstruction for Erdős–Straus surfaces*, Bull. Lond. Math. Soc. **52** (2020), no. 4, 746–761. doi:10.1112/blms.12374; arXiv:1908.02526.
- [2] C. Elsholtz and T. Tao, *Counting the number of solutions to the Erdős–Straus equation on unit fractions*, J. Aust. Math. Soc. **94** (2013), no. 1, 50–105. doi:10.1017/S1446788712000468; arXiv:1107.1010.
- [3] P. Erdős, *Az $1/x_1 + 1/x_2 + \dots + 1/x_n = a/b$ egyenlet egész számú megoldásairól*, Mat. Lapok **1** (1950), 192–210.

- [4] E. J. Ionascu and A. Wilson, *On the Erdős–Straus conjecture*, Rev. Roumaine Math. Pures Appl. **56** (2011), no. 1, 21–30; arXiv:1001.1100.
- [5] L. J. Mordell, *Diophantine Equations*, Pure and Applied Mathematics, Vol. 30, Academic Press, London–New York, 1969.
- [6] S. E. Salez, *The Erdős–Straus conjecture: new modular equations and checking up to $N = 10^{17}$* , arXiv:1406.6307, 2014.
- [7] R. C. Vaughan, *On a problem of Erdős, Straus and Schinzel*, Mathematika **17** (1970), 193–198.
- [8] K. Yamamoto, *On the Diophantine equation $4/n = 1/x + 1/y + 1/z$* , Mem. Fac. Sci. Kyushu Univ. Ser. A **19** (1965), 37–47.